

Terraforming Sahara

Weather control will make Sahara habitable and the most advanced mega-city ever build on Earth

Abstract

Weather control has been a subject of science fiction for decades, but in recent years scientists have proposed the idea that one day, controlling and using it, is going to be feasible and very useful to serve humanity's needs.

Body

Controlling the weather will make possible to “terraform” the great and vast desert of Sahara. If scientists can control the weather, they can also send rain in specific locations on Earth, thus reducing the space that is dry and unused in the Sahara territory. Controlled rain led by scientists, will make the desert of Sahara to gradually become green and useful, thus making it habitable by future humans. The rain will be “send” at the edges of the desert, thus gradually reducing the dry part and hopefully one day, even make the whole surface useable and wet.

Having such a great empty surface area will make it possible one day to build a huge mega-city of the future, capable of hosting a population greater than any country on Earth.

Conclusion

Controlling the weather one day will make possible for scientists to send targeted rain in specific areas of the desert of Sahara, thus even making it habitable and green. With such a great area at their disposal, humanity can even build a huge mega-city of the future with a capacity far greater than any other country on Earth. A true manifestation of science and technology used for the common human good.

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Albi Ndoni
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